

Participatory Knowledge Report - Düsseldorf 2025

Successful R&I in Europe 2025 Conference - Düsseldorf 2025

Author:

- **Codrin Dinu Vasiliu:** Romanian Academy - Iasi Branch / Academia Română - Filiala Iași

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Word Clouds. Keywords and Narrative Frames

➔ Knowledge Ecosystems ↔ Dusseldorf ↔ March ↔ Cluster 5 ↔ Cluster 6 ↔ Artificial Intelligence ↔ Horizon Europe ↔ Digital transformation ↔ Creative Industries ↔ Health ↔ Systems Thinking ↔ Networking ↔ Liege ↔ Soil Mission ↔ Europe ↔ Living Labs ↔ Bioeconomy ↔ Participatory Knowledge ↔ Space Research ↔ Agrifood ↔ Energy ↔ Mobility ↔ Natural Resources ↔ Technology Networks ↔ Scaling ↔ Multiplying ↔ Multi-actor Systems ↔ Innovation ↔ Projects ↔ COST Actions ↔ Astronomical Heritage ↔ FAIR Data ↔ Digital Twin Technologies ↔ European Health Systems ↔ Parallel workshops ↔ Dynamic Ecosystems ↔ Data-driven Decisions ↔ Value Chain ↔ Resilience and Sustainability ↔ Cultural Heritage ↔ Biobanks ↔ Circular economy ↔ Future Food ↔ Research Management ↔ Rawshaping ↔ Knowledge Anthropology ↔ Widening Countries ↔ National Contact Points ↔ Pre-Conference Actions ↔ ENoLL ↔ Policy Labs ↔ Turkey ↔ Germany ↔ Holland ↔ France ↔ Spain ↔ Italy ↔ Armenia ↔ Republic of Moldavia ↔ Ukraine ↔ Poland ↔ Romania ↔ Participatory Governance ↔ Migrants ↔ Space Exploration ↔ Heritage ↔ TRL ↔ Cesar ➔

Short introduction

Context

Successful R&I in Europe 2025 Conference is an event where actions are organized to develop networks, partnerships and alliances in programs funded by the European Commission. The focus was on Pillar 2, the Horizon Program, for all clusters, from 1 to 6, but the interactions also discussed programs and actions from the other Pillars (1 and 3).

The event focused on:

- Series of presentation workshops for best practice models
- Socialization events to establish partnerships.

Through the dynamics of interaction phenomena, the emphasis was placed on:

- Digital technologies and new challenges of the interaction between anthropological, ecological and digital systems
- Frontier technologies, with disruptive effects in economics and societal systems
- Resilience and sustainability in agrifood systems
- Security management in data systems, products, communities and values
- Space exploration and the use of space systems as horizons of exploration not only for new realities, but also for new ways of thinking and understanding
- Valorization of heritage in multicultural contexts
- Artificial Intelligence in health and quality of life systems
- Knowledge is considered again and again the base for sustainable and inclusive development, but the attention is on the complex understanding, systems thinking, critical thinking, exploratory co-creation, raw thinking shaping, intelligent communication

Specific Problems

ARFI and the Cesar Consortium have the following specific problems, with significant negative effects in the development of externally funded projects and in knowledge transfer actions, through which research results have an impact on society:

- Lack of a consolidated hub for digital technologies, especially artificial intelligence
- Lack of a consolidated hub for knowledge management in transfer, innovation and development actions
- Lack of a consolidated hub for research in technical fields, which can be integrated with research in socio-human fields

- Lack of permanent resources for integrating ARFI and Cesar into permanent strategic alliances and partnerships, at European and global level

Objectives

For the ARFI and Cesar systems, by participating in this event, the following objectives were established:

- Establishing the basis for collaboration models and methodologies and integration into alliances and networks in knowledge ecosystems.
- Identifying indicators of understanding for new knowledge and action systems at European level
- Establishing the basis for collaboration for a hub dedicated to disruptive digital technologies
- Establishing the basis for collaboration for a hub dedicated to a new network of living labs, centered on Living Labs INN (LLINN www.llinn.rdrp.org)
- New partners for agrifood programs, knowledge ecosystems

Transversal Objective

The main cross-cutting objective was to re-enhance project proposals that were rejected in European programs.

Notes

Raw Information

(1) Among the participants, interest was expressed in participating as partners in consortia. Interest in research and innovative activities seems higher than taking the lead in project management.

(2) ARFI and any Cesar partner become interesting for other organizations especially in the following situations and through the following types of activities:

- Research activities in the socio-human fields
- Research Management Activities
- Evaluation Management Activities
- Sustainability Management Activities
- Models, Methodologies and Best Practices
- Living Labs building and coordinating
- Stakeholder communities building

-
- Coordinating proposals in Horizon
 - Coordinating proposals in European Research Council
 - Match-making activities and tools

(3) Research management, knowledge transfer, resilience and sustainability are pillars in any project and action.

(4) The collaborations with teams in Romania were appreciated by the participants who opened this topic.

(5) Companies are especially interested in Horizon projects. SME are interested too. A lot of researchers have their own SME. This fact allows them to be very dynamic in alliances.

(6) Living Labs are still highly appreciated, but at levels of conceptualization that Cesar think tank has already structured:

- On the living lab - policy lab chains
- Under cluster or hub umbrellas
- With a strategic objective to become a Demonstrator and Lighthouse
- As independent, autonomous, and unconsolidated as institutional structures
- As bottom-up structured knowledge and action groups

(7) Digitalization should no longer be missing from any strategic project or action.

(8) For research activities, relationships must also be strengthened with universities that are not necessarily at the forefront. Sometimes universities that do not appear at the top of rankings are more active in developing Horizon projects.

(9) Interest in economic impact and statistical evaluation of knowledge is decreasing. Interest in economic and societal impact is increasing.

- The Dora Declaration, Jena Declaration, Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information are more and more important in the European Programs Ecosystem.
- I observed irritation among three participants from private research environments when discussing the WoS and Hirsch rating systems.
- In this regard, solutions must be found that maintain the advantages for both evaluation paradigms.

(10) Participation in such events should become a regular activity for anyone working in knowledge production and transfer. In addition, maximum effects occur when participating in teams.

(10) Organizations from the Republic of Moldova and Ukraine are extremely active. Similarly, there is an acceleration of emergence in the case of organizations from Georgia, Armenia and Africa, in terms of their presence in European research, innovation and development networks. Organizations in Romania can become hubs of collaboration and communication with these systems.

Media - 6 March 2025

Media - 7 March 2025

Networking

During the event, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu focused on peer-to-peer discussions, aiming to establish direct communication channels. This was also noted by some of the participants on their own social media networks.

Sascha Devigne · 3rd+ · ✓ Following ×
 Chefredakteur bei STUDIO...
 38m · 🌐

From Duisburg to Europe: AI in Journalism on the International Stage 🌐

Today, I had the opportunity to speak at the innovation conference "Successful R&I in Europe" about AI-powered automation in journalism and our work at **STUDIO 47** – and what can I say? A fantastic event!

- ◆ A highly engaged, international audience – great questions and inspiring discussions about the future of AI and media.
- ◆ Valuable connections with researchers, innovators, and businesses interested in our AI tools and their scalability across Europe.
- ◆ Exciting perspectives for future projects and collaborations – the potential is huge!

A big thank you to the organizers from **ZENIT GmbH** and **EEN NRW / NRW.Europa** – and of course, to the amazing conversation partners who joined me today in deep discussions about innovation, AI, and media: **Maik Bohne**, **Codrin Dinu Vasiliu**, **Robert E. Wendrich**, **Alexandru Stan**, and **Algirdas Baciška**. It was a pleasure! 🙌

Now, it's time to take these insights forward and keep working on making AI a meaningful asset for journalism – and expanding its impact across Europe!

(Photo by Alexandru Stan)

Potential partners

Participants with whom communication channels for projects and alliances have been discussed and established.

Successful R&I in Europe 2025 Conference

Dusseldorf 6-7 March 2025

Participatory Knowledge Report - Codrin Dinu Vasiliu

CONSULTING FACILITARE

Bavarian Research Alliance

Dr. Amarachi Kalu
Scientific Officer
Environment, Energy & Bioeconomy

Bavarian Research Alliance GmbH
Prinzregentenstrasse 52, D-80538 Munich
Phone: +49 (0)89 9901 888-121, Fax: -29
Twitter: @BayFOR_UEB
kalu@bayfor.org, www.bayfor.org

NKS Klima, Energie, Mobilität | KEM
Nationale Kontaktstelle zum EU-Programm Horizont Europe

CL5

Dr. Maik Scholz
National Contact Point Climate, Energy and Mobility
Project Management Jülich | Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH
Wilhelm-Johnen-Straße | 52428 Jülich, Germany
Phone: +49 2461 61-85588 | E-mail: m.scholz@fz-juelich.de
www.nks-kem.de

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Joyce Kao
Co-Executive Director

+49 177 4068203
joyce.kao@digiresacademy.org

Bayerstrasse 77C
80335 Munich, Germany

DRA
DIGITAL RESEARCH ACADEMY

Nurogames GmbH
Schaafenstr. 25
50676 Köln / Cologne
Deutschland / Germany

www.nurogames.com

Jens Piesik
Dipl.-Wirt.Ling.
Managing Director

Office +49 221 398 80846
Mobile +49 151 234 56926

jens.piesik@mgt.nurogames.com

fir an der RWTH Aachen
Campus-Boulevard 55
52074 Aachen - Germany

Stephanie Harfensteller, M.Sc. M.A.
EU-Project Management
EU-Research Manager

+49 241 47705-160
+49 163 8412378
Stephanie.Harfensteller@fir.rwth-aachen.de

fir.rwth-aachen.de

Coatema
Coating Machinery GmbH

Thomas Kolbusch
Leitung Vertrieb / Marketing / Technologie + Prokurist
Director Sales / Marketing / Technology + VP

tkolbusch@coatema.de
T +49 21 33 97 84 120

COATEMA Coating Machinery GmbH
Roseller Straße 4 • 41539 Dormagen • Germany

MEMBER OF ATH www.coatema.com

IIS WASABI 2.0

LIÈGE université
Gembloux Agro-Bio Tech

Wallonie

IIS WASABI 2.0

Françoise Bafort
Internationalization

Gembloux Agro-Bio Tech
Av. Maréchal Juin 13, 5030 Gembloux
Belgium

+32 81 62 24 33
francoise.bafort@uliege.be
www.wasabi2.org
IIS Wasabi 2.0

ZENIT

Dr.-Ing. Uwe Birk
Dipl.-Ing.
Consultant

ZENIT GmbH
Bismarckstraße 28
45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr
Germany

T | +49 208 30004-49
M | +49 151 - 551 094 49
E | bi@zenit.de
@ZENITGmbH

LC Innoconsult INTERNATIONAL
SZEGED - BUDAPEST - HONG KONG

H-6723 Szeged
Felső Tisza-part 31-34.

www.lcinnoconsult.com

Dr. MOGYORÓSI Péter
Director, CEO

mogyorosi.peter@lcinnoconsult.com

+36 30 978 4215

SPACE ERA GERMANY

KAIF ALI
FOUNDER & CEO

+49 15753083810
+91 9899609188
kaif.ali@spaceera.de

@kaifali4sdg

Sanderstraße 196
Wuppertal 42283
Germany

Const. build enviro energy

SOLARIS 5

Christa Ivanova, PhD
Head of European partnerships

christa.ivanova@microfluidic.fr
(+33) 1 88 33 43 68
microfluidics-innovation-center.fr

Paris, France

MEXT

QR code

Onur Dedeoğlu
Turkish Employers Association of Metal Industries (MESS)

Sascha Devigne
Chefredakteur

0203.47 993 46
s.devigne@studio47.de

STUDIO 47
Auf der Höhe 10
47059 Duisburg
Fon 0203.47 993 47
Fax 0203.47 993 45
info@studio47.de
www.studio47.de

rawshaping technology

robert e. wendrich
0031 (0)653917004
info@rawshaping.com
www.rawshaping.com

UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE.

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ANNEX 1 - Conference Agenda and Official Presentation

(presentation according to the official website - <https://horizont.zenit.de/en/events/successful2025/>)

The conference invites researchers and entrepreneurs from North Rhine-Westphalia and all other regions throughout Europe to find new research and innovation (R&I) partners for Horizon Europe projects. Participants are invited to give a short presentation (ideas and/or results) with a focus on Horizon Europe calls, where a budget of approx. € 95.5 billion is available up until 2027. The networking event is structured in parallel workshops focussing on eight topics:

- Cluster 1: Health
- Cluster 2: Creative Industries
- Cluster 4: Digital Technologies
- Cluster 4: Industrial Technologies
- Cluster 5: Energy
- Cluster 5: Mobility
- Cluster 6: Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment
- Innovation Procurement (PCP/PPI)

The event addresses in particular universities and research institutes as well as companies, especially small and medium-sized enterprises. Participants are invited to become involved in established and new technology networks between researchers, entrepreneurs and multipliers related to Horizon Europe.

Thursday Agenda, 6 March 2025 (Day 1)

Including exhibition: Innovations for Europe based in NRW

Conference Moderator: Dr. Bernd Janson

Opening session <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Thorsten Menne, Director Research Funding, Research Policy, Ministry of Culture and Science of North-Rhine Westphalia
Keynote speech <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Birgit Weidel, Head of Department, Innovation Ecosystems, SMP/Entrepreneurship & Consumers, EISMEA, European Commission
Success stories in Europe based in NRW <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ENEXA, Dr. Michael Röder, Paderborn University• Flex2Energy, Thomas Kolbusch, Coatema Coating Machinery GmbH, Dormagen
Services for Proposals and Projects

- Hans H. Stein, Managing Director, ZENIT GmbH

Session 1: Parallel workshops

European projects seeking partners

Digital Technologies

A New European University Alliance – UNIVERSEH

- Sonja Bretschneider, Heinrich Heine Universität, Germany

Multi-modal data integration

- Dr Andrew Spink, Noldus Information Technology, Netherlands

Security and Privacy of Large Language Model (LLM) Integrations

- Dr Koen Gilissen, PXL University of Applied Sciences & Arts, Belgium

Architectures and Design Methodologies to Accelerate AI Workloads

- Professor Stefania Perri, University of Calabria, Italy

Decoding Human Brain Architecture with Artificial Intelligence

- Dr Christian Schiffer, Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH/Projekträger Jülich, Germany

Artificial Intelligence for Advancing Particle Accelerators

- Dr Joseph Wolfenden, University of Liverpool, Great Britain

Transforming Astronomical Heritage through AI-Driven Digitization and Accessibility

- Dr Simon Anghel, Astronomical Institute of the Romanian Academy, Romania

Cognitive Digital Twins with General Purpose AI for Dynamic Intelligent Systems

- Mahdi Bohlouli, Petanux GmbH, Germany

Generative Concept-based Perception, Control and Manipulation (G-COPCOM)

- Peteris Racinskis, Institute of Electronics and Computer Science (EDI), Latvia

Industrial Technologies

Pilot-Plant Plasma Processes: From Alcohol to Graphene

- Tim Hülsler, Institut für Umwelt & Energie, Technik & Analytik e. V. (IUTA), Germany

Mechatronic Principles from Semiconductor Manufacturing to Next-Generation Beamline Equipment

- Ronald Timmermans, MI-Partners, Netherlands

Compact automation systems for chemical handling

- Dr Kishan Thodkar, zHS AG, Switzerland

From FAIR Data to Trusted AI: Recent Advances and Applications of Generative AI

- Dr Anas Abdelrazeq, RWTH Aachen University – Chair of Intelligence in Quality Sensing (WZL-IQS), Germany

The coal fly ash of Ukrainian thermal power stations as secondary source to recover the REEs

- Professor Mykola Kharytonov, Dnipro State Agrarian and Economic University, Ukraine

Hybrid kiln for brick and roof tile production

- Dr Denny Mathew Alex, Institut für Ziegelforschung Essen e.V., Germany

Innovative plasma spray based fabrication Technology of Metallic Coatings for welded joints used in marine applications

- Dr Alaa Abou Harb, MGM STAR CONSTRUCT SRL, Romania

The Decarbonisation Factory project, recognized as a flagship initiative by the state government of NRW and the United Arab Emirates, is aimed at revolutionizing sustainable manufacturing in various industries, with a focus on mobile interior applications

- Dr Steffen Hohenstein, The Aviation AM Centre, Germany

Digital Twin Technologies for Industrial Applications

- Rahul Tomar, DigitalTwin Technology GmbH / Nurogames GmbH, Germany

How to measure sustainability impact of technology innovation for Horizon Europe

- Christopher Zimdars, Umtec Technologie AG, Switzerland

Mobility

Rail-Based Mobility Concepts: Exploring Small Autonomous Vehicles like MONOCAB for Passenger and Cargo Use Cases

- Martin Griese, Ostwestfalen-Lippe University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Germany

An auction-based cooperative delivery coordination platform

- Dávid Csercsik, Pázmány Péter Catholic University, Hungary

Municipal owned EV charging stations for greener mobility

- Salome Zajbert, Municipality of Eilat, Israel

Increasing the production efficiency of metallic bipolar plates by pre-coating in a roll-to-roll PVD arc process

- Nils Fredebeul-Beverungen, Fraunhofer IWS, Germany

Motorcycle safety initiative

- Jiří Babický, Motorcycle safety Initiative, Czech Republic

Simple, robust and cost-effective lasers for LiDAR applications in aviation and space

- Bastian Gronloh, RUPHOS – Rugged Photonics Systems GmbH, Germany

Health

Investigation of the possibility of increasing the degree of binding of an antitumor drug to tumor DNA using innovative technology of non-ionizing and non-thermal millimeter electromagnetic radiation

- Dr Vitali Kalantaryan, Yerevan State University, Armenia

Transforming European Health Systems through Digital Innovation

- Ilka Gomez, SpinLab Accelerator GmbH, Germany

Production of human-derived collagen and hyaluronic acid

- Atakan Özer, Genkord Health and Biotechnology Services INC., Turkiye

New building blocks for medical chemistry

- Professor Vitalii Palchykov, Oles Honchar Dnipro National University, Ukraine

PHOENIX SEP – Single Entry Point for Nanopharmaceuticals

- Dr Eleonora Rizzi, PHOENIX OITB gGmbH, Germany

The Impact of Metabolic Dysfunction-Associated Steatotic Liver Disease on Sepsis Immune Responses (SepsisFAT)

- Dr Neven Papić, University Hospital for Infectious Diseases Dr. Fran Mihaljevic, Croatia

Innovative Health Research and International Collaboration: Vilnius University Faculty of Medicine

- Dr Dominyka Dapkute-Sadauskiene, Vilnius University, Lithuania

Microfluidic instruments and flow control for biology applications

- Dr Lisa Muiznieks, Microfluidics Innovation Center, France

Development of an intelligent Controller for Pediatric Insulin Pumps Powered by a renewable energy

- Professor Dorsaf Elleuch, mes, Tunisia

Session 2: Parallel workshops

European projects seeking partners

Digital Technologies

Advanced Virtual Prototyping and AI Compiler technologies

- Professor Rainer Leupers, RWTH Aachen, Germany

On EU Education, Research & Innovation (ERI) – Towards An Enhanced Strategic Framework, Humane Technology and Social-Cultural Resilience.

- Dr Robert E. Wendrich, Rawshaping Technology Research & Innovation (RST), Netherlands

New encryption-decryption technology for high security cloud content using Digital Twin

- Dr Rajarshi Sanyal, Proximus, Luxembourg

Digitalization of Landscapes and Determination of Primary Soil Parameters to Optimize Energy Inputs

- Dr Egidijus Katinas, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU), Czech Republic

On Device AI Agents: Revolutionizing Real-time API Interactions with Privacy Preserving Intelligence

- Dr Mustafa Taha Kocyyigit, Bogazici University, Turkiye
AI in human-robot collaboration
- Kristina Bardos, Scientific Association for Mechanical Engineering, Hungary
EduDefend – AI-Powered Cybersecurity for Digital Learning
- Professor Thorsten Kliewe, European Alliance for Digital and Green Education (EDGE), Spain
Dynamic Digital Twins: Pioneering Sustainable Innovation in Construction, Manufacturing, Smart Cities & Semiconductor
- Dr Tariqul Islam, DigitalTwin Technology, Germany

Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment

Fostering regional bioeconomy transition: Collaborating to build circular bioeconomy model regions

- Dr Denise Gider, Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ) GmbH, Germany

Microfluidics in Food and Environmental analysis

- Dr Christa Ivanova, Microfluidics Innovation Center, France

Assuring food security and biodiversity in times of climate change through technology and innovation

- Dorothea Streich, Kreis Lippe, Germany

Regenerative agriculture in the Netherlands (ReGeNL) and the international opportunities

- Ingrid van Huizen, Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, Netherlands

Assessing Agricultural Systems for Ecosystem Restoration, Productivity, and Economic Sustainability

- Dr Françoise Bafort, University of Liege – Gembloux Agro-Bio Tech, Belgium

Microbial Power Reactors for Resource Recovery and Energy Vectors

- Fabian Fischer, HES-SO University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Western Switzerland, Switzerland

High Quality Plasma Activated Water Production via Reinforcement Learning

- Dr Hüseyin Oktay Altun, Boğaziçi University, İstanbul, Türkiye

Energy

NextGen Renewable Biofuels

- Himanshu Himanshu, TH Köln (Cologne University of Applied Sciences), Germany

Reimagining carbon in Eilat – tailoring a CCUS Strategy

- Salome Zajbert, Municipality of Eilat, Israel

Data-driven Decisions for Regional Utilities: AI and Data Analytics for Municipal Utilities and Grid Operators

- Jan Pohl, bofest consult GmbH, Germany

Developments in infrastructure modelling

- Dr William Facett, Cambridge Architectural Research Ltd, United Kingdom

Nitrogen-Doped Graphene Derivative for High Energy Density Supercapacitors

- Dr Veronika Šedajová, Palacký University Olomouc, Czech Republic

Innovative Complex Alloys for Enhanced Bipolar Plates in PEM Electrolyzers: Collaborate to Advance the Hydrogen Economy

- Maximilian Steinhorst, Fraunhofer IWS, Germany

Industrialised Circularity in the Build Environment Value Chain

- Chris Leinders, PXL University of Applied Sciences & Arts, Belgium

Heat Pipe Technology Adaption (for different energy or industrial applications)

- Elmar Bartlmae, European Science Communication Institute (ESCI) gGmbH, Germany

Health

STOP-MASH, a first-in-class approach to combat fatty liver disease

- Professor Juergen Eckel, CureDiab Metabolic Research GmbH, Germany

Next-Generation Combination Approach for Muscle-Invasive Bladder Cancer Treatment

- Dr Nina Bondarenko, DNIPRO STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY, Ukraine

AI-Based Microbiome Engineering for Next-Generation Phage Therapy

- Dr Balázs Ligeti, PPCU-FITB, Hungary

Epidemiology of antimicrobial resistance; Human microbiota in health and disease

- Professor Arjana Tambić Andrašević, University Hospital for Infectious Diseases Dr. Fran Mihaljevic, Croatia

Photoactive polymer composites for the production of biocompatible and immunospecific prosthetic materials

- Dr Olena Fesenko, Institute of Physics of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine

Artificial Intelligence in Drug Design: A Faster Path to Therapeutics

- Professor Şener Özönder, ArtificaX Technologies, Turkiye

Clinical Interactive Exposure Therapy

- Mariam Draeger, Spoonrift Games, Germany

Beebird Technology – User-Friendly and Accessible Solutions in Digital Health

- Serap Duman, Beebird Technology, Turkiye

Friday Agenda, 7 March 2025 (Day 2)

Including exhibition: Innovations for Europe based in NRW

Conference Moderator: Dr Bernd Janson

Services for Proposals and Projects

- Jan Skriwanek, National Contact Point Health, DLR-PT

Success stories in Europe based in NRW

- Psych-STRATA, Professor Bernhard Baune, University of Münster
- CERTAINTY, Dr. Andreas Schmidt, SINGLETON BIOTECHNOLOGIES GmbH, Cologne

Session 3: Parallel workshops

European projects seeking partners

Health

Triboelectric Bioactive 3D-Nanofibrous Bandage for healing deep Wounds

- Professor Amir Fahmi, Hochschule Rhein-Waal, Germany

Investigation, development and optimization of new innovative drug formulations for various therapeutic indications

- Professor Franciska Erdő, Pázmány Péter Catholic University, Hungary

Work with half of Europe with partners from the Innovative Public Procurement Project: Procure4Health

- Dr Marcin Kautsch, Sucha Beskidzka Hospital, Poland

Possible determining role of disturbance of molecular structure of intracellular water in formation of malignant neoplasms and its restoration by non-ionizing microwave radiation

- Dr Vitali Kalantaryan, Yerevan State University, Armenia

Hyperspectral Imaging-Based Personalized Health Monitoring

- Şahin Mete, Bewell Technology, Turkiye

Looking for project team to jointly apply for a Horizon Europe call in the field of molecular biological diagnostics

- Dr Birgit Omengo, Inno-train Diagnostik GmbH, Germany

AI-Driven Transitions to Active Retirement among Adult Workers with Mental Health Problems

- Ozlem Koseoglu Ornek, Witten/Herdecke University, Germany

Enhancing Research Through Statistical Consulting

- Dr Kainat Khowaja, Helmholtz Zentrum München, Germany

Creative Industries

Circular Design and Sustainability Assessment for Developing Innovative Product-Service-Systems

- Dr Manuel Bickel, Wuppertal Institut für Klima, Umwelt, Energie gGmbH, Germany

Mobility Methodologies that support Researchers' knowledge transfer skills. EdTech Talents' best practices.

- Dr Janika Leoste, Tallinn University, Estonia

Role of Immersive Technologies towards visual communication in Real estate and infrastructure sector

- Kaif Ali, Space Era Germany UG, Germany

Generative AI for fashion design & photography

- Jens Piesk, DigitalHealth Technology GmbH / Nurogames GmbH, Germany

Cultural Heritage: Metamorphoses and Metaverse in Virtual Museums

- Dr Viktorya Vasilyan, The Institute of Archaeology and Ethnography NAS RA, Armenia

Revolutionizing Regional News: AI-Powered Automation in Journalism and the Innovative Tools of STUDIO 47

- Sascha Devigne, STUDIO 47, Germany

Creative Industries in Poland

- Aleksandra Szymańska, Polish Creative Industries Development Center, Poland

Artificax

- Professor Şener Özönder, Artificax, Türkiye

Cultural Fabric

- Federica Casaccio, ACEEU GmbH, Germany

Regenerative Textile Industry

- Zsafia Kollar, Human Material Loop BV, Netherlands

Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment

Climate Resilient Bioeconomy

- Professor Peter Kern, TH Köln (Cologne University of Applied Sciences), Germany

Opportunities in Climate Research: Call for Fair Climate Policies

- Octavian Holtz, BayFOR – Bayerische Forschungsallianz, Germany

INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS IN GREEN AGRICULTURE: BIODEGRADABLE COMPOSITIONS OF COMBINED EFFECT BASED ON AGRICULTURAL WASTES

- Dr Aram Mikaelyan, Agrobiotechnology Scientific Center (SC), Armenia

MyBiotech – Innovator for Pharmaceutical Development & Bioprocessing

- Matthias Jourdain, MyBiotech GmbH, Germany

S2AQUAcoLAB: bridging science and industry for a resilient aquaculture sector

- Dr Cátia Marques, S2AQUA Laboratório Colaborativo, Associação para uma Aquacultura Sustentável e Inteligente, Portugal

Process development and optimization for resource recovery

- Franziska Blauth, Institut für Umwelt & Energie, Technik & Analytik e.V., Germany

Transition into Sustainable Process Industries

- Professor Axel Gottschalk, SUPREN GmbH – sustainable process engineering, Germany

Energy

High Temperature Technologies for Emerging Energy Applications

- Dr Siri Harboe-Minwegen, OWI Science for Fuels, Germany

INTEGRAPV: Integrated Solutions for Sustainable, Efficient, and Circular Photovoltaic Energy

- Professor Ali HMIDET, ISTMT, University of Tunis El Manar, Tunisia

Battery Cooling Solutions

- Professor Gamze GEDIZ ILIS, IDD Energy, Türkiye

Agentic AI & Digital Twin Technology for Green Energy Transition

- Christian Tismer, Agentic AI & Digital Twin Technology for Green Energy Transition, Germany

Expertise and facilities in the area of power electronics, power hardware-in-the-loop techniques, and distribution grid in Centre for industrial electronics, SDU, Denmark

- Dr Ramkrishan Maheshwari, University of Southern Denmark, Denmark
Industrial decarbonization through latent heat thermal energy storage solutions
- Dr Alba Jiménez Pagán, Greendur, Spain
Drop-in capability of Renewable Fuels for climate-friendly mobility and heat generation
- Dr Sangeetha Ramaswamy, OWI Science for Fuels gGmbH, Germany
Cathode Active Materials for European Market
- Dr Azadeh Motealleh, Shift Materials, Norway
AI Powered Battery Management System
- Mehmet Emre Aslakci, MEATEC, Turkiye

Session 4: Parallel workshops

European projects seeking partners

Health – Amsterdam 3

Fimo Health – A flexible platform for CE-marked therapy companions in chronic diseases

- Tim Fellerhoff, Fimo Health, Germany

The role of population biobanks in the development of medical intelligence platforms for translational research and precision medicine

- Dr Gidre Kvedaraviciene, Vilnius University, Faculty of Medicine, Lithuania

PATHWAI-2-ATMPs: Process Analytical Technology & AI for Scalable ATMP Manufacturing

- Dr Riccardo Marega, CER Groupe, Belgium

Emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases – immunopathogenesis and molecular epidemiology research

- Professor Alemka Markotić, University Hospital for Infectious Diseases Dr. Fran Mihaljevic, Croatia

Centrifugal microfluidics for personalized health and diagnostics

- Dr András Laki, Pázmány Péter Catholic University, Hungary

Antigen-specific TIL production in cellular adoptive immunotherapy for cancer treatment

- Professor Gürsel Turgut, Genkord Health and Biotechnology Services INC., Türkiye

Collaboration opportunities with EATRIS, the European Infrastructure for Translational Medicine

- Martin De Kort, EATRIS ERIC, Netherlands

Our mission: Rethinking radiological analysis

- Matthias Kraemer, VGMorph GmbH, Germany

Digital Technologies

SIGNAL IDUNA Group – a project partner for Data & AI innovation

- Anastasia Walter, SIGNAL IDUNA Gruppe, Germany

AI Regional Innovation Valley collaboration

- Ingrid Meijer, Oost NL, Netherlands

DigitalTwinSphere: Advancing AI-Driven Digital Twins for Resilience Across Sectors

- Professor Amila Akagic, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

An explainable machine learning method for predicting and understanding protein interactions

- Professor Gergely Katona, University of Gothenburg, Sweden

Innovative Collaboration Across Disciplines: Advancing Research, Education, and Impact

- Dr Jovan Shopovski, European scientific institute, Macedonia

IT service provider for Research and Innovation EU projects

- Dr Gianluca Rossi, Ro Technology srl, Italy

AI-Driven Foundation Model for the developments of Tailored Tool Steels and High-Strength Aluminium for Giga-Casting Applications

- Anwar Hamasaiid, ROVALMA, S.A., Spain

Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment

Advancing Bio-Based Materials: Integrating Modular BioBricks for Innovative Production Solutions

- Dr Marisa Sárria Pereira de Passos, RWTH Aachen University, Germany
System Solutions for the Creation of Quadruple Helix Economic Models in Regional Development – RHCE (Regional Hub for Circular Economy)
 - Michal Dlapka, NARA-SK, Slovakia
Advanced Spectroscopic Sensors and Digital Platforms for Future Food Safety and Quality Monitoring
 - Dr Cristina Fernandez Avila, IRIS Technology Solutions SL., Spain
Innovative Bio-Based and Renewable Filament Yarns: Advancing Sustainable Textile Solutions Topic: Development of bio-based yarns leveraging advanced polymer technologies, renewable resources, and closed-loop systems to contribute to circular economy
 - Deniz Savci, POLYTEKS TEKSTIL SAN ARAS VE EGT A.S., Turkiye
The Future Food Factory OWL: A Research Hub for the Food Production of the Future
 - Sebastian Wittland, University of Applied Sciences and Arts Lemgo, Germany
Bioactive peptides for prevention of chronic diseases
 - Ana I. Fernandez Salina, CER Groupe, Belgium
Biological Alternatives for Seed Treatment: Enhancing Stress Resilience, Agronomic Performance, and Economic Viability in Crop Production
 - Dr Marcus Weinmann, LUFA Speyer, Germany

Industrial Technologies

- 6G Ambient IoT Networks – From Vision to Deployment
 - Dr David Starke, Fraunhofer Institute for Microelectronic Circuits and Systems (IMS), Germany
Technology Centre Prague offer for Horizon Europe projects
 - Jiri Janosec, Technology Centre Prague, Czech Republic
Expertise and R&I facilities of the Technical Faculty of Southern Denmark University – Robotics, Automation, Software engineering, Electronics
 - Professor Kaspar Hallenborg, SDU Faculty of Engineering, Denmark
Industrial Additive Manufacturing of Elastomers
 - Dr Barthel Engendahl, Chromatic 3D Materials GmbH, Germany
Enabling Europe’s industrial and climate goals by improving materials durability and friction reduction in components. How do you start?
 - Dr Dirk Drees, NV FALEX TRIBOLOGY, Belgium
The “Sustainable Stone by Portugal” project
 - Dr Marta Peres, Association Cluster Portugal Mineral Resources, Portugal
Trustworthy AI through user-centered transparency
 - Johanna Werz, RWTH Aachen University – Chair of Intelligence in Quality Sensing (WZL-IQS), Germany
Employing Plasma Technology for Medical Implant Production through the Synthesis of Fiberglass-Reinforced Hydroxyapatite Layers on the Surface of Titanium Alloy or the Synthesis of Hydroxyapatite Layers on the Surface of Fiberglass-Reinforced Titanium All
 - Dr MOHAMMEDALQASIM ALSABTI, MGM STAR CONSTRUCT SRL, Romania
INFRACHIP: AN EU HE Project Enabling Free Access to state-of-the-art technologies accross Europe for future of the industry
 - Eda Cig Turktas, Silicon Saxony, Germany

Annex 2 - ARFI and Cesar Promotional Materials

The materials were printed with the support of Rural Development Research Platform, within the RoRuralia laboratory, in synergy with the Cesar Center.

Systems Thinking Innovation Living Lab
 Cesar Cluster 2 - Knowledge Ecosystem Cluster - www.cesar2030.eu

Coordinator: Codrin Dinu Vasiliu www.cesar2030.eu
CodrinDinuVasiliu@gmail.com

MISSION: Systems Thinking Living Lab - STILL3

- Researching, and developing the systemic dimensions of knowledge ecosystems, to support participatory knowledge within innovation labs, living labs, and stakeholders community.

Knowledge actions and capacity building for:

- Scientific research, Knowledge transfer, Methodology, Strategic reports
- Living Labs, Policy Labs, Lighthouses, Demonstrators, Co-creation hubs
- Stakeholder communities, Multi-actor systems, Communities of practice
- Resilience agency, Synergies, Sustainability, Decision-making intelligence

Knowledge lifecycle

Participatory Knowledge → Scientific Research → Open Knowledge → Knowledge Transfer → Participatory Governance → Strategic Knowledge → Knowledge Recycling

Policies lifecycle

ACADEMIA, CHIC, BUSINESS, GOVERNANCE

Systems Thinking Living Lab
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

Organic Food Living Lab
Cesar Cluster 1 - Agri-Food Cluster

Coordinator: Ioan Sebastian Bruma www.cesar2030.eu
SebastianBruma1978@gmail.com

OFL encompasses interdisciplinary collaboration
 from fields such as agronomy, rural development anthropology, biotechnology, ecology, microbiology, marketing, statistics, and agricultural economics, related to:

- Organic ecosystems,
- Urban and rural food systems,
- Biodiversity conservation,
- Climate change mitigation and adaptation,
- Nutritional quality of organic food,
- Soil health and regeneration & Water conservation,
- Economic viability and market dynamics,
- Education, knowledge transfer, business models.

OFL is developing research and knowledge transfer to support:

- Interdisciplinary research that integrates knowledge from diverse fields such to address complex challenges in ecological agro-food systems.
- Socio-economic dimensions of organic agriculture and food production, with a focus on resilience, biodiversity conservation, and resource efficiency.
- Innovative technologies and practices to enhance farming systems, agriculture 3.0, agroecology, organic and sustainable soil management.
- Policies for bio agri-food systems, including subsidies, incentives, certification schemes, and regulatory frameworks.
- Understanding the consumer behaviour related to organic products and health.
- Capacity building and education programs for students, farmers, policymakers, and other stakeholders.
- Collaboration between academia, government, industry, civil society, and local communities to promote knowledge exchange, innovation, and collective action.

Organic Food Living Lab
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

Cattle4Future Living Lab
Cesar Cluster 1 - Agri-Food Cluster

Integrated Living Lab for Sustainable Dairy Systems

Coordinator: Andra Sabina Neculai-Valeanu www.cesar2030.eu
Sabina.Valeanu@gmail.com

Key Focus Areas and Activities

Sustainable Dairy Farming Practices

- Feed additives and management practices to lower methane emissions.
- Renewable solutions, such as anaerobic digesters for manure management.
- Promote rotational grazing to enhance soil health and biodiversity.

Smart Dairy Technologies

- Deploy IoT sensors to monitor milk yield, cow health, and feeding patterns.
- Test robotic milking machines for efficiency and labor reduction.
- Big data analytics to optimize milk production and improve product quality.

Dairy Product Innovation

- Functional foods, protein-enriched, lactose-free, and probiotic-rich products
- Sustainable packaging alternatives: plant-based and biodegradable materials.
- Consumer testing to refine new product prototypes.

Animal Welfare and Ethical Practices

- Improved housing systems to enhance cattle comfort.
- Use wearable devices to monitor stress and health metrics.
- Develop guidelines for ethical dairy farming in collaboration with stakeholders.

Circular Dairy Economy

- Repurpose dairy by-products into energy sources or value-added products.
- Produce biofertilizers from manure to support sustainable agriculture.
- Reuse water efficiently in dairy processing.
- Educate the community on the benefits of a circular dairy economy.

Cattle4Future Living Lab
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

CultFood Living Lab
Cesar Cluster 3 - Visual Narratives Cluster

Coordinator: Petronela Savin www.cesar2030.eu
Savin.Petronela2015@gmail.com

Research Domains - Methodological approaches

◊ anthropological approaches ◊ ethnographic approaches ◊ ethnological field research ◊ field experiment ◊ sensory ethnography ◊ ethnohistorical and comparative approaches ◊ patrimonialization of foods and behaviours ◊ patrimonialization of cuisine ◊ objects and museums ◊ digitization of food heritage ◊ ethnolinguistic approaches ◊ psychological approaches ◊ sociological approaches ◊ approaches from the perspective of communication theory ◊ food knowledge ◊ knowledge transfer strategies ◊ knowledge transfer platforms ◊ nutrition education intervention ◊ food-related academic programs ◊ community-based solutions ◊ science for communities and community for science ◊ awareness ◊ responsible research and innovation

www.cultfood.living-laboratory.eu

Thematic directions

- Food and society
- Food and religion
- Food and politics
- Food and marketing
- Food and family
- Food and body
- Food and psyche
- Food and nature
- Food and time
- Food and space
- Food and discourse
- Food and digital space

CultFood Living Lab
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

GLOtTO - Linguistics Actions Living Lab

Cesar Cluster 3 - Visual Narratives Cluster

Coordinator: Elena Isabelle Tamba

www.cesar2030.eu
isabellefamba@gmail.com

Mission - To tell the Food Story...

GLOtTO mission and objectives are aligned with its purpose of fostering interdisciplinary research, innovation, collaboration, and sustainability in the food ecosystem, putting the language in the center as the main vector of cultural expression and identity element.

Food as a Language # Linguistics # Food Linguistics # Cultural Expression # Lexicography # Onomastics # Toponymy # Anthroponymy # Dialectology # Brands # Names # Ethnolinguistics # Food Discourse Strategies # Memory # History of Food # Food Culture # Food Words Story # Food in Phraseology # Tradition Linguistics # Family # Humour # Knowledge Transfer # Regional food # Discourse of recipes # Substitute # Artisanal food # Industrial food # Imported food # Translation # Semantics # Labels # Influences # Linguistic strategies # Nomenclature # Gastronomic vocabulary # Consumer comprehension # Relation brand plate name # Food and Diaspora # Field investigations # Oral vs Written # Synchronic and Diachronic Analysis # Terminology Dynamics # Pragmalinguistics # Sociolinguistics # Oral Sharing of Recipes # Popular culinary terminology # Linguistic Creativity # Teaching Resources # Food-related practices # Popular knowledge # Traditional knowledge # Stereotypes # Audiovisual documents # Cartographic Form # Linguistic Maps # Research methodology # Interdisciplinary perspective # Ethnolinguistic experiment # Traditional dishes # Digitization of cultural resources # Etymological study # Semantic pattern # Culture-nature relationship # Collective imaginary # Cross-cultural and cross-linguistic perspective # Ontological component of language #

Selected Topics

- **Food Words Story:** Food terminology, Food and Onomastics, Food in Phraseology, Multimedia Platform for food terms (Dictionary & Atlas & other digital resources)
- **Linguistic Mapping in Space and Time:** Linguistic Contact Gastronomic Diaspora, Recovery of gastronomic linguistic heritage elements
- **Food speech today:** Healthy living or marketing strategies: Food Discourse strategies (oral vs. written), Analysis of current gastronomic recipes
- **Food Linguistics knowledge transfer**

GLOtTO - Linguistics Actions Living Lab
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

Innovative Bio(nano)composite Systems

Coordinator: Dr. Habilit. Carmen-Mihaela Popescu mihapop@icupp.ro

Researcher areas

- ★ **Bio(nano)composite hydrogels**
- ★ Superabsorbent hydrogels for soil fertilisation and water retention
- ★ Functional biobased hydrogels for wastewater decontamination
- ★ Multifunctional hydrogels for wound healing

Bio(nano)composite formulations for coating and adhesives

- ★ Superhydrophobic nanocomposite formulations for paper and wood /wood based products
- ★ Synthesis of composite formulations via Pickering emulsion polymerisation
- ★ Antimicrobial nanocomposite formulations for paper and wood/wood based products
- ★ Biocomposite adhesives for medium densified fibreboards (MDFs)

Bioactive materials for food packaging for extended shelf-life

- ★ Pretreatment techniques for cellulosic based materials: plasma, γ -irradiation, enzyme and mercerization
- ★ Surface modification of cellulosic based materials with bioactive formulations

Sustainable composite systems

- ★ Sustainable multifunctional packaging materials
- ★ Reactive processing of the composite systems
- ★ Compatibilization and plasticisation

Bioactive materials for food packaging for extended shelf-life

- ★ Pretreatment techniques for cellulosic based materials: plasma, γ -irradiation, enzyme and mercerization
- ★ Surface modification of cellulosic based materials with bioactive formulations

Wastes valorisation

- ★ Lignocellulosic waste valorisation for extraction of high value products
- ★ Natural and Synthetic polymers (i.e. recycled PP) waste valorisation for new biodegradable materials

Wastes valorisation

- ★ Lignocellulosic waste valorisation for extraction of high value products
- ★ Natural and Synthetic polymers (i.e. recycled PP) waste valorisation for new biodegradable materials

Development, degradation, modification and protection of wood and wood based products

- ★ Degradation processes affecting historic wood, effect of different degradative factors (fungi, T, RH and UV light) and degradation mechanisms involved in wood and wood based products degradation
- ★ Development of composite materials for structural applications (i.e. WPC)
- ★ Thermal and chemical modification of wood
- ★ Formulations with superhydrophobic and antibacterial properties for wood, wood based products

Advanced characterisation techniques

- ★ Evaluation of materials by using FT-IR spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, NIR spectroscopy, 2D-COS IR spectroscopy and chemometric methods
- ★ Migration testing for food contact materials

- ★ Water sorption properties, sorption kinetic and interactions between the matrix and the water molecules; gas permeability tests
- ★ Rheological behavior of composite materials is solid and liquid gel state

Immersive Performance Living Lab

Cesar Cluster 3 - Visual Narratives Cluster

Coordinator: Andreea Tatiana Grigore

www.cesar2030.eu
INSTAGRAM: @a.tatianagrigore

Teaching emotional communication by Performing Arts

The privilege of a lifetime is to become who you truly are.
Carl Gustav Jung

Creative actions have a significant impact on raising and improving the human beings.

These actions encompass a wide range of activities and effects:

- Economic Growth and Job Creation
- Cultural Enrichment and Social Cohesion
- Personal Well-Being and Mental Health
- Innovation and Technological Advancement
- Global Influence and Cultural Diplomacy

Creativity is vital to raising and improving the living standards of human beings. Innovation drives economic growth, enhance cultural and social well-being, support mental and emotional health, and contribute to global innovation and sustainability. By investing in and supporting our cultures of creativity, the societies can foster a more enriched world for all.

MiRRorinG Immersive Performance Living Lab
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

TIES Hub - Interspecies Living Lab

Cesar Cluster 4 - Societal Innovation Cluster

Coordinator: Irina Frasin

www.cesar2030.eu
IrinaAda@gmail.com

Scope

- To promote research, education and outreach in the field of human-animal interaction, in connection with the main objectives and mission of the Cesar2030 Center of Excellence.
- To encourage multi and interdisciplinary approaches for knowledge transfer in all humans and other animals systems.

Objectives

- Research and knowledge production
- Incremental and Transformative Innovation
- Knowledge transfer in multi-actor systems
- Policy, Advocacy, Decision Making Support
- Humane Education
- Stakeholders Communities Support

TIES Hub Mission

- Exploring, mapping, researching, and presenting the anthrozoology ecosystems, to increase awareness for participatory knowledge and inclusive biopolitics.

TIES Hub - Interspecies LL
is an innovative hub within Cesar2030 ecosystem

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 - FILL - Food for Iasi Living Lab
 - OFLI - Organic Food Living Lab
 - Innovative Bio(nano)composite Systems
 - ICAR - Innovative Technology
 - FLIT - Food Transilvania
 - HAS - Food Health & Safety
- Visual Narratives Cluster** (Cesar Cluster 3)
 - CultFood Living Lab
 - Birds R2 - Sociolinguistics
 - H360 - History Living Lab
 - GLOHO Lingua Living Lab
 - MOARA - Moara Culturală
 - GERTRUDE - Performance Hub
- Knowledge Ecosystem Cluster** (Cesar Cluster 2)
 - STILL3 - Systems Thinking LL
 - Cesar Academy Living Lab
 - EPSA - Policies & Strategic Actions
 - PLL - Project Logistics Living Lab
 - Emergent Systems Living Lab
 - DECK Living Lab
- Societal Innovation Cluster** (Cesar Cluster 4)
 - RULL - Rural Development LL
 - TIES Hub - Interspecies LL
 - RODIA - Diaspora Living Lab
 - ZAHERA
 - GastroTOUR Living Lab
 - DHALL - Digital Humanities LL
 - RESYST - Resilient Systems

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KAPIMS Model Cities2030 Project D3.3 Systems Thinking Methodology

Coordinators
Tuula Löytty, Codrin Dinu Vasiliu

Ioan Sebastian Brumă, Lucian Tanasă ,
Mark Koetse, Justine Vanhalst,
Kyriakos E. Georgiou, Edna Yamasaki,
Dernet Osmancelebioglu, Bruno da Silva,
Sebastian Doboş, Kalle Karlsson

Project Cities2030 (101020-B) 101000640
On creating resilient and sustainable food systems towards 10002030

Deliverable D3.3 describes the process and results that embrace a methodological and logical framework for Cities and Regions Food Systems to apply Systems Thinking. The provision responds to the following questions:

- What are the issues in Cities and Regions Food Systems?
- Why is it important to find solutions to these issues?
- How to make sense of urban food systems' interconnections?
- What are scenarios and best solutions?

The evolution of the D3.3 includes participatory activities, an application of pre-existing models, and pioneer exploitation of novel ICT tools. The results are leverageable in any work package.

- **Scientific research.** Fundamental, applied, and experimental research with impact in rural and urban socio-economics.
- **Knowledge transfer.** The development of participatory knowledge projects, with a particular focus on sustainability, disability, circular economy, healthy living, environmental protection, and cultural, material, and immaterial heritage.
- **Systemic mapping and analysis:** The development of the scientific infrastructure for the identification, analysis, and evaluation of the determining factors for the economic environment, social environment, quality of life, cultural heritage, and natural environment.
- **Strong, multi-stakeholder communities:** The development of communities of stakeholders, following the Quadruple Helix model, engages the main actors from the academic environment, the entrepreneurial environment, governance, and civil society.
- **Knowledge ecosystems:** the development of systemic infrastructures based on knowledge and participatory governance for the intelligent growth of rural and urban socioeconomics.

Rural Development Research Platform

Personal Note

Text in Romanian

Poate e doar un gând și cred că nu poate fi mai mult decât o simplă sugestie. Sau cel puțin un concept preliminar într-o posibilă metodologie.

În domeniul meu de interes, despre care hai să zicem că se cheamă antropologia cunoașterii, mi-am dat seama că mă ajută mult o echipă transculturală. Poate că sunt și puțin supărat pe limitările pe care le văd în sistemul nostru. Dar mă simt foarte bine în grupuri care au de împărțit, în mod deschis, mai curând idei și obiective, decât indicatori de plan. Făcând, bineînțeles, o minimă selecție, pentru că oportunități sunt peste tot.

Am făcut, de exemplu, acum, la Dusseldorf, ca și altă dată, în Finlanda, niște propuneri unor oameni cu care am discutat cu mare plăcere ore în șir. Și mi-am dat seama că de la astfel de oameni ar trebui să plece clubul de tip living lab în care aș vrea să fiu.

Astfel, STILL3 (Systems Thinking Living Lab) va avea obiectiv transcultural de extindere, nu doar în domeniile de lucru, ci și în comunitatea de la baza acestuia.

În plus, cred din ce în ce mai mult că fiecare laborator de tip living lab, având ca obiectiv principal acțiuni de experimentare și inovare pe perioade medii și lungi, în medii de interacțiune directă, trebuie să se dezvolte pe bazele unei comunități a producției și transferului de cunoaștere. Dincolo de limbajul de lemn, toate acestea înseamnă că avem nevoie să construim echipe dinamice cu interese de cunoaștere similare.

Astfel, pentru fiecare living lab, chiar înainte de a gândi acțiuni în programele Horizon, Erasmus și ERC, trebuie avute în vedere și programe COST Actions, Marie Curie (MSCA) și chiar programe de finanțare regionale și locale.

#Cesar2030 #STILL3

Text in English

Maybe it's just a thought and I think it can't be more than a simple suggestion. Or at least a preliminary concept in a possible methodology.

In my field of interest, which let's say is called the anthropology of knowledge, I realized that a transcultural team helps me a lot. Maybe I'm a little angry about the limitations I see in our system. But I feel very good in groups that have to share, openly, ideas and objectives rather than plan indicators. Making, of course, a minimal selection, because opportunisms are everywhere.

For example, now in Dusseldorf, as I did in Finland, I made some proposals to people with whom I enjoyed talking for hours. And I realized that the living lab club I would like to be in should start from such people.

Thus, STILL3 (Systems Thinking Living Lab) will have a transcultural objective of expansion, not only in the fields of work, but also in the community based on it.

Furthermore, I increasingly believe that every living lab, with its main objective of medium- and long-term experimentation and innovation in environments of direct interaction, must develop on the basis of a community of knowledge production and transfer. Beyond the wooden language, all this means that we need to build dynamic teams with similar knowledge interests.

Thus, for each living lab, even before considering actions in the Horizon, Erasmus and ERC programs, COST Actions, Marie Curie (MSCA) programs and even regional and local funding programs must be considered.

#Cesar2030 #STILL3

Acknowledgement

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ENG: Codrin Dinu Vasiliu's participation in this series of events was funded by the Romanian Academy - Iași Branch, as support for innovation and development actions. The action also represents support for strengthening the capacity of the Cesar center in the ante-factum (pre-implementation) period.